

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part : XIV Some Derivatives of 1-Arylamino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane

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3,4-Dimethylcyclohexanone is condensed with a number of primary arylamines and aqueous potassium cyanide in presence of glacial acetic acid to yield 1-arylamino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-nitriles. These nitriles are converted into their corresponding amides and acids and only one isomer in each case is isolated.

A NUMBER of 1-arylamino-2-, 3-, and 4-methyl cyclohexane-1-cyanides, their amides and acids were prepared by Bukhsh, *et al.*¹. These anilino compounds have lately gained importance, on account of being the starting materials for the synthesis of cycloalkenyl nitriles and carboxylic acids which find use in polymerisation reactions and preparation of number of these have been patented²⁻⁴. With the increased importance of arylamino compounds, the present communication describes the preparation of some tetrasubstituted derivatives of cyclohexane, 1-arylamino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-nitriles, -acid amides and -acids.

Thus, 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexanone was condensed with aniline, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline and α -naphthylamino⁵ to afford 1-arylamino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-nitriles (I, X = CN). Hydrolysis of these to the respective amides (I, X = CONH₂) was carried out according to the method of Bukhsh, *et al.*¹ and the acids (I, X = COOH) by hydrolysis with 40% sulphuric acid. *o*- and *m*-Anisidines, *m*-xylydene, *o*-chloroaniline, 2,4-dichloroaniline, *p*-phenetidine and *m*- and *p*-nitroanilines failed to undergo this condensation.

The hydrolysis of the nitriles and amides proceeded smoothly except in the case of 1- α -naphthylamino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid amide where sulphonation in preference to hydrolysis had occurred. Further, nitriles on keeping unlike the cycloheptane and cyclo-octane analogues did not isomerise to the isonitriles^{6,7}.

Only one isomer each of the nitriles, acid amides and acids was isolated; the homogeneity of all the compounds was tested through t.l.c. and the acids

were characterised through their S-benzylisothiuronium salts. IR spectra of 1-anilino-, *m*- and *p*-toluidino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids in nujol revealed that these exist as Zwitter ions of the type II (1620-1610 cm⁻¹ and 1395-1390 cm⁻¹: C-O antisymmetric and symmetric stretching of $\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{C} \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right\} -$; group of bands at 2700-2200 cm⁻¹: ν_s NH₂⁺ and NH₂⁺; 1550-1545 cm⁻¹; δ NH₂⁺ of secondary amine salts) whereas 1-chloro- and 1-bromoanilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids exist as free acids (1705 cm⁻¹: $\nu > \text{C} = \text{O}$ of -COOH; 3315 cm⁻¹ sec. amine N-H stretching vibration).

This difference in behaviour can be attributed to electron withdrawing property of the halogen atom which helps in pulling the electrons away from nitrogen and this makes lone pair less available for sharing thereby inhibiting the formation of NH₂⁺.

Experimental

1-Anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-nitrile: To a solution of 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexanone (3.15 g; 0.025 mole) and aniline (2.33 g; 0.025 mole) in glacial acetic acid (12 ml) was added a solution of potassium cyanide (3.25 g; 0.05 mole) in water (10 ml) with shaking. An oily layer immediately separated out, which solidified after keeping for two days at room temperature. The solid was filtered, washed, dried, and 1-anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanide was crystallised as colourless flakes from benzene-petrol (40°-60°), m.p. 97°. (Yield: 2.7 g; 41.2%). (Found: C, 78.7; H, 8.7. C₁₅H₂₀N₂ requires C, 78.9; H, 8.8%). All the other cyanides are entered in Table 1

1-Anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid amide: 1-Anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-cyanide (2 g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) and after keeping for 48 hours at room temperature, the contents were poured over crushed ice and made alkaline with liquor ammonia. The separated solid was filtered, washed and dried; 1-anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid

TABLE 1. 1-ARYLAMINO-3, 4-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE-1-OYANIDES

S. No.	Arylamino group	Solvent	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			
						Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Benzene-petrol (40-60°)	101-2	50	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂	79.2	8.8	79.2	9.1
2.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	"	96	64	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂	79.1	8.9	79.2	9.1
3.	α -Naphthylamino	"	127-8	51	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂	82.1	7.7	81.9	7.9
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	"	136	61	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ Cl	68.3	7.0	68.5	7.2
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	"	128	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ Br	58.5	6.3	58.6	6.1

TABLE 2. 1-ARYLAMINO-3, 4-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE-1-CARBOXYLIC ACID AMIDES

S. No.	Arylamino group	Solvent	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			
						Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Benzene-petrol (40-60°)	142	81	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₂	73.5	9.2	73.8	9.3
2.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	dilute ethanol	129	87	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₂	73.7	9.3	73.8	9.3
3.	α -Naphthylamino	"	151	61	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ ON ₂	76.8	8.1	76.9	8.1
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	"	122-3	65	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl	64.2	7.7	64.1	7.9
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	"	129	69	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Br	55.3	6.2	55.3	6.4

TABLE 3. 1-ARYLAMINO-3, 4-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE-1-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

S. No.	Arylamino group	Solvent	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis				S-benzyl isothiuronium salt m.p. °C
						Found C	% H	Requires C	% H	
1.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Dilute ethanol	207	64	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	73.4	8.7	73.5	8.8	163
2.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	"	206	67	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	73.5	8.7	73.5	8.8	150
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	"	176	61	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	63.8	9.0	63.9	8.8	154
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	"	161	61	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ NBr	55.3	6.2	55.2	6.1	160

amide was crystallised from benzene-petrol (40°-60°) in colourless flakes, m.p. 138° (Yield: 1.85 g; 84%). (Found: C, 72.9; H, 8.8. C₁₅H₂₂ON₂ requires C, 73.1; H, 9.0%). The other acid amides prepared in an analogous manner are entered in Table 2.

1-Anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid. The above acid amide (1.5 g) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (12 ml), water (15 ml) was added during cooling in ice and the mixture refluxed on a sand bath for 6 hours. The contents were cooled, neutralised with liquor ammonia, and acidified with glacial acetic acid. The deposited solid was filtered, washed and dried; *1-anilino-3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid* was crystallised from dilute ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 199°-200°. (Yield: 2.1 g; 69%) (Found: C, 72.6; H, 8.4. C₁₅H₂₁O₂N requires C, 72.8; H, 8.5%).

Its S-benzylisothiuronium salt crystallised from dilute alcohol had m.p. 195°.

All the other acids similarly prepared are entered in Table 3.

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